

Attitudes Towards the Use of Technology among Lecturers of College of Education

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History Received: August 21,2020 Accepted: October 18,2020	<i>This research is devoted to study the Iraqi EFL lecturers attitudes towards the use of technology in the field of EFL learning. It aims at theoretically investigating the advantages of this employment and practically studying the Iraqi EFL lecturers views and attitudes based on this employment. The present study falls into four chapters. The first chapter gives a general background for the present research , in terms of its problem , aims , hypothesis , procedure , limits and value . The second chapter deals with the main theoretical views concerning the modern increase of the employment of technology in learning English as a foreign language. Chapter three includes a questionnaire which is made for the lecturers from the College of Education, Mustansiriyah University to measure their overall evaluation and attitudes towards the use of technology in EFL learning, based on their teaching experiences and performance. The fourth chapter summarizes the main conclusions and findings of the present study.</i>
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1. Introduction

Modern technology became an essential part of our daily life , and its employment has its own advantages and disadvantages . Learning a foreign language is not an exception , i.e. the employment of technology in learning has also brought considerable advantages and subsequent disadvantages . Based on this fact , the present study aims at investigating the Iraqi lecturers attitudes towards the employment of technology , and the extent to which electronic learning (henceforth e- learning) provides a supportive remedy for educational purposes . The study hypothesizes that Iraqi lecturers find e-learning an advantageous requirement for learning English as a foreign language . The procedure adopted can be summarized in a theoretical overview towards the merits and demerits of the employment of e-learning , and providing a questionnaire to measure the extent to which Iraqi EFL lecturers find e- learning a supportive requirement for EFL learning . The study is hoped to shed light on e- learning advantages and disadvantages , and give a better understanding for more fruitful learning environment . The study falls into four sections , an introduction in which the problem , aims , hypothesis , procedure , limits and value are presented . The second section provides theoretical views and considerations concerning e-learning and the employment of technology in learning . The third section , however , is concerned with the lecturers attitudes and evaluations concerning e- learning . Finally , section four sums up the main conclusions and findings arrived at , and presents some suggestions and recommendations .

Section Two :

The recent increase of using internet applications nowadays offers various opportunities for many people in various parts of the world . Thus , the internet and its related technology has , indeed , become a major medium for communication leisure , research and study . This fact increased considerably after the spread of covid-19 , which made all governments , institutions , and individuals focus on internet and its related applications to fulfill their needs and requirements .

One of the possible reasons (regardless of health care and safety) is that the internet gives its users various opportunities in many different applications . It can be argued , therefore , that the increased application of technology and internet is a major source of knowledge and information that can be gained quickly to a vast number of people , being (i.e. the internet technology) able to go beyond any sort of limitation of space and time . Warren et.al. (1998: 53) agree that the application of internet and its related technology offers two basic advantages ; communication and its related strategies as well as access to information and knowledge in various fields and subjects . Similarly , Park (2009 : 93) lists eight internet functions or advantages that can be recognized in the field of education . These can be put as follows :

- a) The internet is a comprehensive store of data .
- b) It offers a wide range of infinite communication .
- c) It provides online interactive education and learning .

- d) It supports electronic direct research .
- e) It keeps its users in touch with global innovations and discoveries .
- f) It improves and supports learners' and teachers' interests in learning .
- g) It is the best medium for global learning .
- h) It can carry and show various sorts of information , schemes , programs and catalogues .

Furthermore , when we consider the employment of modern technology in e-learning , a major advantage that can be recognized is that teachers , learners (and even common people) can get any bit of information they need quickly , easily and with low cost in comparison with the traditional methods of learning and research . We can reach any piece of knowledge anytime , anywhere (school , library , home , bus) while carrying our own computer , eye-pod , or smart phone .

In relation to what has been already mentioned , Park and Biddix (2008 : 104) realize that , as time passes , new digital forms of technology have been widely employed in various educational institutions . Charp (2000 : 10) agrees with Ciglaric et.al (1998 : 497) that internet employment in educational fields and applications had , indeed , the potential to improve and support the quality of the educational process owing to the facilities and interests that are offered by the internet , under the condition that both of lecturers and learners do their best to get the required aims .

Despite all the above mentioned advantages and considerations , Lawal (2006: 56) states that , on the other hand , traditional teachers could be reluctant (or pessimistic) in reflecting their own attitudes and perceptions towards any sort of change in the educational process . This sort of pessimism is probably caused by teachers' lack of awareness concerning the policies and potential benefits information communication technologies have to the development of learning process .Oladosu (2012 : 74) says that teachers' awareness focuses on their understanding , appreciation and recognition of the benefits woven around information communication technologies in the education process , and their own inclination towards its adoption and employment .

For educational purposes, it is clear that technology is widely employed to gather required information , to do research or to add to the teachers' and learners' knowledge in various subjects and issues .Therefore , internet plays a major role in modern education. It is certainthat , in this modern era , everyone prefers internet and its related technologies for their queries, problems or needs . Similar to what has been previously said , it is obvious that popular search engines (as Google, Yahoo, etc.)represent the best choice of people as they provide an easy reach to the vast pieces of information within just a few seconds. It contains a wide range of knowledge that can be easily obtained at any time. The internet has , thus , introduced great improvements in the fields ofcommunication , technology , and online entertainment as well .

Today, owing to covid-19 spread and its subsequent reactions and results ,it has become a more significant and powerful tool in the present world that is preferred by all .

As far as the field of education is concerned , the employment of technology and e-learning are crucial requirements because they are characterized by their :

1. Affordable and cost effective education .

It is well known that one of the greatest barriers to education is high cost. The Internet supports and improves the quality of education, which is (i.e. education) one of the cornerstones of sustainable development of any nation.

2. Teacher - student and peer interaction

The internet has allowed teachers to be in constant touch with their students or with other fellow classmates with the help of social media, messaging apps and chat forums. In addition , parents , for instance , can interact as well as communicate with teachers and school authorities about their kid's performance and development in the school. This interaction helpsboth teachers and students to explore new ideas and enrich their experiences and knowledge.

3. Effective learning and teaching tool

Teachers can use the technological innovations as a teaching tool by , for example , posting their teaching materials , such as lectures , notes and videos on website or any other forum . The learning process , henceforth , becomes more interesting and diverse with the employment of tutorial videos and related topics .

4. Easy access to highly qualifiededucation

Lecturers and students can easily access high quality education materials such as tutorial videos on YouTube for free in most occasions . They can also make use of the internet by providing their students with extra resources and study material as interactive lessons, educational. Teachers and lecturers can easily record their lectures and send it to their students for revisions which is , of course , better than reading from notebooks .

5. Teachers' and learners' interaction with digital media .

Regular employment of digital media is one of the essential parts of our daily lives. Digital boards , for example , save paper, they are important for displaying videos and audios to attract students' attention. Recently, there appearedvarious paid sites which give education resources that are extremely rich in their quality and easily understandable to everyone when compared with traditional or classical learning strategies .

6. Keeping lecturers updated with latest findings and information

Information is one of the biggest advantages offered by the internet. There is a vast amount of information available for every topic. Modern technology, henceforth, keeps lecturers and learners up to date with the latest findings regarding the subjects in which lecturers and learners are interested.

7. Learning with the aid of multimedia

Modern technological innovations encourage the students during the learning process simply because it helps to simplify the given material. Also, it helps to visualize what is being taught by the lecturers in the classroom.

How can teachers be successful in e-learning ?

Many specialists in the field of education mention some factors that can be considered by teachers with reference to e-learning and the employment of technology. In this sense, Pope (2020) suggests that a lecturer with a new remote class should follow these six tips:

1. Find the right technology: If a teacher wants to be successful in online e-learning, the first thing he'll need to do is to find a reliable online platform or learning system to help him communicate and cooperate with his own students.

2. Set possible expectations for students' behavior: In general, students may not be used or motivated to doing classes online. They might consider e-learning as an opportunity for them to relax (a little bit too much). Therefore, it is very important for the teacher to discuss what's expected of students and what they can expect from him during the online lectures. The teacher must talk to his students about the types of activities they can participate in. Also, it's a good idea for the teacher to discuss and address any doubts or difficulties they might have, especially when matters come to technology. Bullying and improper behavior can also be something lecturers have to expect. Whether a lecturer is addressing adults, teenagers, or children, it's very important that (s)he sets out certain behavioral remarks and guidelines before launching a particular course.

3. Community building: Building a proper connection in a particular online English class is relatively harder than in a traditional face-to-face teaching environment. Despite the fact that video conversations are effective, they simply cannot be regarded equal to being in the same classroom. For this reason, it's important for lecturers to establish a sense of community among their learners, in order to let them feel part of the educational group and want to go on learning together. For example, having a private group and encouraging students' work together on various given projects may help lecturers overcome such a problem.

4. Careful time management: A lecturer can easily fill his (or her) schedule with online classes – and then find himself (or herself) overloaded. Thus, a lecturer must keep enough time to prepare every class properly.

5. Benefit from as many as free online resources and cites: In the website, there are numerous free online resources for online English lecturers and their students. These are very necessary sources of information for both of lecturers and students.

6. A successful lecturer should collaborate with other English lecturers:

Many online lecturers sometimes find themselves a little isolated. It's, therefore, a considerable idea to be in touch with other local or foreign lecturers to collaborate and exchange knowledge and experiences, and establishing an online staffroom experience.

Methods

3.1 Participants

It is worth mentioning here that the participants of the present study were 10 EFL lecturers who teach the English language in different departments in Mustansiriyah University, College of Education, five of them were males and other five were female EFL lecturers.

3.2 Instrument

As far as the present study is concerned, the researchers adopted a version that represents 'self-efficacy or attitudes scale on educational employment of the internet and its related technologies', that was prepared by Sahin (2009). There were twenty chosen positive items with five choices that express lecturers attitudes as "I'm completely sufficient", "I'm quite sufficient", "I'm sufficient", "I'm a little sufficient", and "I'm insufficient", where the participating EFL lecturers were asked to choose the best alternative that expresses their attitude for each given statement.

3.3 The procedure

The researchers addressed the EFL lecturers and asked them to write their responses to the answer sheet. Then, lecturers replies to the given scale were carefully computed so as to take the overall scores.

3.4 Results

As stated earlier, twenty items were given to the EFL lecturers, ranging between five = "I'm completely sufficient" and one = "I'm insufficient". The highest mark was fifty, and the lowest mark was ten. Accordingly, the lecturers whose scores were between 40-50 were considered as "good" lecturers, indicating positive attitudes towards the employment of technology in EFL teaching. The lecturers whose scores ranged between 26-39 were considered as "average" lecturers, indicating average

attitudes towards the employment of technology in EFL teaching , whereas lecturers whose responses ranged between 10-25 were “ not good ” , which implies negative lecturers’ attitudes towards the employment of technology in teaching English as a foreign language . The results arrived at can be stated in Table (1) below .

Table (1) EFL lecturers self- efficacy attitudes towards using the internet and technology for educational purposes

Marks	Accepted as	Percentage
40-50	Good	50 %
26-39	Average	40 %
10-25	Not Good	10 %

As shown by Table (1) , it can be seen that 50% of lecturers stated that they were “ good ” , expressing satisfactory attitudes towards the use of internet and technology in EFL teaching , whereas 40 % stated that they were “ average ” , as far as their attitudes are concerned . Finally , 10 % of the lecturers clearly stated that they were “ not good ” , which subsequently indicates negative attitudes towards the employment of the internet and its related technologies in teaching English as a foreign language .Topics that EFL lecturers feel sufficient in while they employ the internet and its related technologies include :

- 1-Using the internet search engines as yahoo , google , etc.
- 2-Using electronic dictionaries
- 3-Establishing connections with other lecturers
- 4-Finding the sources of information on the internet
- 5-Sharing any sort of information with other lecturers
- 6-Downloading photos or texts from the internet for lessons or homework
- 7-Downloading or watching videos
- 8-Translating documents and texts
- 9-Following up events and news in English
- 10-Searching about English resources online
- 11-Getting information about the subject I taught to my class
- 13- Reading articles and recent publications online
- 14- Searching for educational games online
- 15- Reading notes and topics that are relevant to my lessons

On the other hand , EFL lecturers found themselves insufficient , and expressed negative attitudes towards :

- 1- Getting information about regulations and laws online .
- 2- Downloading electronic books .
- 3- Following EFL educational magazines and journals .
- 4- Using database programs .
- 5- Participating in classes and exam applications online .

Conclusions and Findings

Generally speaking , it was obvious that most of the EFL lecturers stated that they were qualified in using or employing the internet and its relevant technology as an educational tool and medium , and only very few participants expressed their inability to employ the internet and its relevant technology for educational purposes, which is a percentage that can be treated in future programs and supportive courses for lecturers . **On the basis of these findings**, it can be concluded that the employment of technology in learning English as a foreign language can definitely improve the quality of English language learning in many ways . It keeps the door open to a wealth of significant information and educational resources , by means of increasing learning opportunities in (and beyond) the classroom . Lecturers and specialists must be encouraged to use online materials to prepare lessons and scientific materials , and learners can definitely use it to expand their range of English language learning .

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